

The role of universities in Sustainable Development Goals: The Erasmus program focus

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ABSTRACT

Education, research, innovation and climate change factors are unequivocally apprehended in a number of Sustainable Development Goals where universities enjoy a first hand-role in addressing these. Universities clench to a nonpartisan position and they help high in the society. This nature directly demands them to educate the public and private sectors on the importance of implementing the SDGs. Universities, under their thorough research credentials and exertions, have a vital role in the provision of necessary and reliable knowledge, evidence-based, answers and coinages to support achieving SDGs. The SDGs provide a platform for the educational institutions to give back to the community by exhibiting their desire, their walking-the-talk tactics and meaningful opportunities to develop their own countries. This anchors the need for this paper in examining the role of universities in achieving the SDGs through research, leadership, and innovation. The paper also examines the barriers towards implementation of SDGs; budgetary, political and resource constraints, globalization, and trade-off of goods and services, lack of positive interlinkages, timescale factor and special scale. The study has a keen interest in the works already done by the European Commission through the Erasmus+ program (2009-2013) and Erasmus+ programs (higher education students, staff mobility programs, and Jean Monnet initiatives). The study also covers how these programs have contributed to collaborations and partnerships with even the third world countries on matters of education, training, innovation, youth empowerment, and research i.e. Konstantinos and Marilena initiatives. All the results identified points that 82 % completion rates which translate to 74% success in achieving SDGs. The paper concludes by urging that; change-makers require the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes that empower them to contribute to sustainable development. Higher education, therefore, is crucial for the achievement of sustainable development.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Mobility program, Higher Education, Third world, European Commission.

1. Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were developed following the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (UNCSD) in 2012 ('Rio+20') and build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDG's) adopted in September 2000 as part of the United Nations Millennium Declaration (UNMD). The SDGs provide a more holistic and integrated approach to development than the MDG's, thus continuing the legacy of the Brundtland Commission (UN, 1987) and the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (UN, 1992). They are designed to be universal and therefore apply to all countries: poor, middle-income and the rich alike, and to all segments of society. Although each focuses on a different topic area, the SDGs; indivisibly and collectively support a development agenda balancing the economic, social and environmental dimensions of sustainability.

The SDGs continue the work of the MDGs, which drove global action to address the basic needs of the world's poorest countries from 2000 to 2015. However, the SDGs differ from the MDGs in several significant ways that make them far more influential and consequential. The SDGs cover a broader range of challenges than the MDGs, most of which are relevant and applicable to all countries or vulnerable groups within countries. They emphasize the linkages between the social, economic and environmental dimensions of sustainable development, as well as between the goals themselves and therefore the need to address the goals in the context of one another; and not separately or sequentially (Nilsson, 2016). They include targets devoted to mobilizing the means required to implement the SDGs, such as partnerships, financing and enabling policies. They recognize that addressing the challenges of the SDGs is everybody's responsibility and explicitly calls on business, civil society, and the tertiary and academic sectors among others to collaborate on the achievement of the SDGs (Guba, 1990).

The main aim of the SDGs is to promote human dignity and prosperity while safeguarding the earth's vital biophysical processes and ecosystem services. While not legally binding, the SDGs do provide a globally endorsed normative framework for development. Governments and other stakeholders must establish national and regional plans for their implementation.

They emphasize that ending poverty and inequality must go hand-in-hand with strategies that support sustainable economic growth, peace, and justice; address fundamental social needs,

including education, health, social protection, and job opportunities; and do all this while also tackling climate change and enhancing environmental protection (Weitz ,N et al.,2014).

The European Union has committed to working towards these goals both within Europe and with its partners abroad. However, recent political changes in Europe and elsewhere put this hope at risk. While the scientific community has emphasized the need for a systematic approach to sustainable development (Stafford, S et al., 2012), policymakers now face the challenge of implementing the SDGs simultaneously with the aim of achieving progress across the economic, social and environmental dimensions worldwide. To increase the likelihood of success for these 17 SDGs, higher education institutions worldwide must teach and train today's students tomorrow's decision-makers – to think both critically and ethically, to learn to cope with ethical dilemmas and apply systems-thinking approaches to serious and complex societal problems (Konstantinos-Loukianos, 2018).

It is with regard that this paper examines the role of universities in achieving the SDGs through research, leadership, and innovation to curb the negative implications that would arise if the SDGs were not achieved. This paper reviews the works done by universities with a keen interest in catalyst initiatives from the Erasmus+ program. The paper utilizes the reviews on these projects from journals, conference proceedings, and thesis reports.

This paper starts by analyzing the SDGs into four categories by giving different schools of thought while providing some of the barriers for their implementation. This is followed by identifying the role of universities in boosting the SDGs and their impacts on the universities and also their contributions to the implementation of the SDGs. The Erasmus+ program and its initiatives in the move to support the universities in the implementation of the SDGs follow suit. The paper finally concludes with the sustainability strategy “whole-institution approach”, meaning all parts of the university community, including external stakeholders, should be involved in the efforts.

2. Sustainable Development Goals

World Economic Forum issues impressive annual reports on the major ‘Global Risks’ facing mankind. To counteract these risks as well as the present mounting disaffection and disruption across the world, partly due to short-term and silo thinking by elites; the SDGs are advocated (Stapleton, 2015), as shown in figure 1.0 below.

Figure 2-1: Sustainable Development Goals

This paper summarizes the SDGs into four schools of thought. They include the well-being goals, economic goals, environmental goals and justice and partnership goals as indicated in figure 2.0.

<p>Well-being Goals (1,2,3,4,5,6,10 and 11)</p> <p>Economic Goals (8 , 9 and 12)</p>	<p>Quality Education : (1) Access to quality education is vital in the job market. Higher Education (HE) provides :social mobility ,empowers people (critical thinking and skills in rapidly changing job market Konstantinos, 2018) (2) (OECD,2013) statistics .People with HE degree are less likely to be unemployed and earn 54% more than holders of upper secondary school education i.e.(Education protects against poverty) .HE graduates are less likely to suffer from depression ;an important factor of health and well-being ,Konstantinos, (2018) (3) University Hospitals. They play a key role in public healthcare systems. They train medical professionals, provide care to millions of patients and conduct research; helps find innovative solutions to cure and prevent diseases and they act as major employers making considerable economic contributions to their region.</p> <p>Thoughts (1) Changing labor market. Caused by globalization, digitization and automation Bhowmik (2017). Hence calling for market and labor retaining and upskilling. (2) (ICSU, 2016) .In Europe, 40% of the youths have a HE degree, which will gradually change due to changing market dimensions. (3) Sustainable development and international links. The concept of Sustainable Development urges that we need to change the way we produce and consume. (4) Universities collaborate with companies, other learning institutions and stakeholders in supporting business incubators. International links are key to nourishing local innovations and achieve sustainable growth.</p>
<p>Environmental Goal (7,13,14 and 15)</p>	<p>Thoughts Research (1) Universities conduct research to identify the relationship between nature and people. E.g the indispensable developments in climate change and global warming as well as their impacts. (2) Indisciplinarity factor: Highlight the interactions of SDGs and mutual reinforcements.</p>
<p>Justice and Partnership Goals (16 and 17)</p>	<p>Thoughts (1) Universities form autonomous partnerships with the governments (local and national) ,civil society and companies with common interest in a bid to implement some of the SDGs ,Selim,S.A. (.2017) (2) Universities facilitate people-to-people contact and are important actors in soft diplomacy. Thousands of mobile students cross borders to gain knowledge about new cultures and bring understanding about their own countries to their hosts (Waibel, 2017). (3) Researchers cooperate around the globe, building networks and developing the knowhow needed to sustain innovation worldwide.</p>

Figure 2: Categorization of the SDGs.

2.1 Barriers towards the implementation of SDGs

Given budgetary, political and resource constraints, as well as specific needs and policy agendas, countries are likely to prioritize certain goals over others. Because of the positive and negative interactions between goals and targets, this prioritization could lead to negative developments for ‘nonprioritized’ goals and targets (Kruger, 2017). An example is the potential prioritization of SDG 2, whose progress might well lead to adverse impacts for several of the SDG 15 targets (on terrestrial ecosystems), for example by converting rainforest to agriculture. Even if countries continue under business-as-usual conditions for agricultural production, terrestrial ecosystems could deteriorate below current levels within a short timeframe (Waibel, 2017).

Moreover, due to globalization and increasing trade of goods and services, many policies and other interventions have implications that are transboundary in nature, such that pursuing objectives in one region can affect other countries or regions' pursuit of their objectives. For example, there could be increased deforestation in some countries because of enforced logging bans in other, often neighboring, countries, or there could be changes in national trading policies that affect the availability of goods and services in other countries. Similarly pursuing a policy for biofuels in one region can drive up prices of food crops elsewhere thus foster a hunger for the poorest; yet, sustainable development of biofuels could also encourage investment and market developments that improve overall food security (Osseweijer et al., 2015; Kline et al., 2016).

However, interactions between SDGs currently have a weak conceptual and scientific underpinning, and there is a clear need for approaches and tools that can support analysis of the nature and strengths of these interactions, and the extent to which they constrain or enable policy and action. Indeed, there is a need to develop guidance and tools that can help policymakers, investors and other actors to identify and manage the benefits and risks of achieving the various goals and targets. In particular, it is important to deploy a more nuanced view of interactions and to move the discourse beyond the simple notion of trade-offs and synergies. For example, Weitz et al. (2014) and (Coopman et al.2016) applied an approach for interlinkages with three categories, supporting, enabling and relying (with sub-categories). International agencies have also published increasingly advanced approaches to identifying and evaluating interactions (e.g. UNESCO, 2016; UN, 2016).

Thinking carefully about SDG interactions and more specifically about the range of different types of interaction is important because they may have very different implications in terms of implementation action. The nature and dynamics of the interactions need to be better understood before the policy can be formulated, including the setting of context-specific (such as National or local) targets and indicators (UNESCO,2017). Such analyses should be conducted with a view to providing a useable knowledge base for both policy-level decision support and the design of implementation strategies.

In short, there is a lack of information on this topic. For this reason, (ICSU, 2016 and Nilsson et al. 2016) have developed a tool, or framework, whereby interactions between SDGs and targets are classified on a seven-point ordinal scale, indicating the nature of the interaction with other targets, and the extent to which the relationship is positive or negative.

3. The role of universities in SDGs

Vocational training centers and research sectors are highly recognized in few SDGs.

However, the universities' boost is needed to achieve all of the SDGs (Bhowmik, 2017). At a glance, the SDGs transverse a wide range of specific sectors namely : agriculture ,health,gender equality,water and sanitation ,energy,industry and innovation,infrastructure ,etc, and under each area,higher education institutions make a huge contribution (figure 3.0).whether in teaching,research,community engagement or advisory services. The unique functions and expertise of universities are very vital for overcoming the interconnected social, economic and environmental challenges which are covered by the SDGs agenda Bhowmik, (2017). Arguably the SDGs will not be achieved without these sectors. (Selim et al.,2017) identifies the key roles of universities under four main categories as :

- Universities can address challenges of SDGs by improvising new innovations, solutions, and knowledge to curb the negative implications.
- Universities can formulate and evaluate result-based policies and establish monitoring mechanisms on progress.
- Since SDGs' accomplishment require a 'wholeness-orientation', universities are in a better position to provide professional and personal skills, capabilities to create future leaders,decision-makers, innovators, entrepreneurs and citizens with knowledge and motivation to contribute.

Universities hold a position of neutral and trusted stakeholders within society. They also have a key role in educating the public and other sectors on the SDGs and in advocating for the importance of the SDGs.Bhowmik, J. et al. (2017) resolves that the engagement of the universities towards the achievement of SDGs is broadly on the merits of research, education, operations & governance and external leadership as indicated in (figure 4.0). His work looks deeply on each contribution and recommends steps towards accomplishing them.

3.1 Learning and teaching

Education is one of the cornerstones of the SDGs.Relevant and quality education leads to sustainable development, which is beneficial to individuals, communities, and countries. As such, universities through their extensive learning and teaching activities (undergraduate and graduate teaching, professional training, executive and adult education, online learning, co-curriculum activities and student clubs and societies) have a critical role to play in SDG achievement UNESCO, (2017).

To contribute to the SDGs through education, universities can.

- Incorporate the SDG agenda and Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) principles into all undergraduate and graduate courses and into graduate research training.
- Offer executive education and capacity building courses for external stakeholders on SDGs and the knowledge needs to address them.
- Structure courses around real-world collaborative projects for chance, where students will have an opportunity to adapt easily in the business world.
- Promote both students and community volunteering activities that address the SDGs.
- Form strong links with the business and industry to monitor employer trends and skills requirements.
- Develop exchange relationships with universities of developing countries and those that address training programs to address SDGs.

Figure 3: Role of universities in SDGs implementation (Source Selim et al.,2017)

3.2 Research

To overcome some of the issues in the SDGs, we will require transforming the manner in which we interact with our planet (IRP,2015). Universities through their detailed and extensive research capabilities and activities have a critical role in providing the necessary

knowledge, evidence-based, solutions and innovations to underpin and support this task (SDSN, 2015). The universities can contribute to research through :

- Support the full spectrum of research approaches needed to address the SDGs including the interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research.
- Advocate for national support and coordination of research on SDGs.
- Support capacity building for developing countries to undertake the use of research on SDGs.
- Encourage and support researchers to engage in global research community efforts to support SDGs (such as international assessments and syntheses of the current state of knowledge).
- Map how universities' researches and research strengths align with the SDGs and identify key researchers.
- Arrange innovation challenges to address SDGs for researchers across the university and external stakeholders.

3.3 Organizational governance, culture, and operations of the university

In their report (SDSN, 2017), it elaborates that universities form the largest entities in the society with wide and distinct social, cultural and environmental backgrounds hence, a significant influence on most of the SDGs. These impacts directly to the implementation of SDGs and by acting responsibly, universities can make significant support in SDG achievements. Various researchers have identified various ways in which universities can contribute SDGs through organizational governance as follows :

- Align university governance structures and operational policies with the aim of attaining SDGs.
- Map how high-level university strategies, policies, plans, and reporting indicators align with the SDGs and identify which organizational units are relevant to specific SDG targets.⁶

3.4 External Leadership

The success in attaining the SDGs will majorly depend on collaborations and partnerships of all actors (Crow, 2019). By leveraging their unique attributes within the community, universities (both individually and collectively) can help to lead, guide and support the local, national and international responses towards SDGs. In support of this idea, Coopman et al. (2016) assert that despite the idea of 'wholeness and collectiveness) in achieving the SDGs,

most countries and the public had little knowledge of the SDGs and little opportunities to actively participate in implementation.

Universities can actively become the key drivers to include the mass generation in the SDG agenda by increasing participation through disseminating knowledge ICSU,(2016). The ICSU report showcases that universities devoted to knowledge creation and teaching for the benefit of the society and also traditionally occupied a critical state that makes them particularly suited to provide leadership on SDG implementation. Therefore, universities can achieve these through :

- Strengthen public awareness and participation in addressing the SDGs.
- Establish and facilitate a cross-sectoral dialogue and action plan on SDG implementation.
- Be on the frontline in policy development and advocacy for sustainable development.
- Demonstrate the commitment and importance of universities in the SDGs implementation.

4. Impacts of SDGs to Universities

The SDG provides a unique platform to higher education institutions to demonstrate their willingness and capability of playing an active and meaningful role in the development of their respective countries and in contributing towards sustainable development Crow, (2019). In line with Erasmus+ (2013-2022), also an opportunity for collaboration and partnerships (Europe- third world, Europe-Europe, and Europe - industrialized countries). Moreover, the importance of sustainable development is recognized in a number of goals, particularly SDG4, which calls for ‘ inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all’ .Many targets within this goal are directly relevant to universities, such s for all learners ‘ to acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development’ Crow, (2019).

The SDGs are global frameworks with strong buy-in and adoption among governments, businesses, civil society, funders, other universities and the community (Huq, 2017). Universities can draw a range of benefits from this broad support by engaging the SDGs. Huq profoundly outlines the benefits as follows :

Universities are rampantly re-designing their curriculum progressively to become both more responsive towards societal needs. This makes them a role model in the society in case of solving global challenges, the greatest strength of the SDG agenda is working together on shared interests. This opportunity allows the universities to form new collaborations and partnerships with governments, related industries and the community in both research and education.,the SDGs communicate to both the youth and the elderly people as global citizens who want to make meaningful contributions to society and the environment. Recently, many organizations have integrated the SDG agenda in their development strategies and also create demand for graduates who are willing to implement the SDG agenda ,the SDGs enlight a new and integrated focus to communicate and display to external stakeholders (governments, funders and the community about the input of the universities to global and local wellbeing and therefore demonstrate their impact and relevance.

5. Erasmus+ mobility schemes

One of the most successful and famous educational mobility programs in the European Union (EU) is Erasmus+, founded in 1987 Stapleton, (2015). The aim was to *promote “dialogue and understanding between people and cultures through mobility and academic cooperation”* (EACEA, 2014). Erasmus+ is one of the EU’s educational exchange schemes, which

contribute to international understanding, stability and sustainable development promoting lifelong learning opportunities. Students are funded to spend a period between three and twelve months in another university of an EU country, which is a member of an inter-institutional network (Brooks et al., 2011).

The Erasmus+ Programme builds on the achievements of more than 25 years of European programs in the fields of education, training, and youth, covering both an intra-European as well as an international cooperation dimension. Erasmus+ is the result of the integration of the following European programs implemented by the Commission during the period 2007-2013; The Lifelong Learning Programme, The Youth in Action Programme, The Erasmus Mundus Programme, Tempus, Alfa, Edulink and programs of cooperation with industrialized countries in the field of higher education.

It was therefore crucial that the Programme was to be associated with a strong brand name that is widely recognized. For this reason, all the Actions and activities supported under the Programme are communicated primarily by using the "Erasmus+" brand name. However, to help participants and beneficiaries of former programs to find their way into Erasmus+, for the purpose of communication and dissemination, the following names are used for those Actions targeting a specific sector, in addition to the common "Erasmus+" brand name, as follows:

- "Erasmus+: Comenius", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively related to the field of school education;
- "Erasmus+: Erasmus", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively related to the field of higher education and targeting Programme Countries;
- "Erasmus+: Erasmus Mundus", in relation to the Erasmus Mundus Joint Masters Degrees;
- "Erasmus+: Leonardo da Vinci", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively related to the field of vocational education and training;
- "Erasmus+: Grundtvig", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively related to the field of adult learning;
- "Erasmus+: Youth in Action", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively related to the field of youth non-formal and informal learning;
- "Erasmus+: Jean Monnet", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively associated with the field of European Union studies;
- "Erasmus+: Sports", in relation to the activities of the Programme exclusively related to the field of sport.

Erasmus program according to (Kruger, 2017 ; Smith 2013) provides a response to the challenges of globalisation faced by European higher education today, in particular the need

to adapt education systems to the demands of the knowledge society, to enhance the attractiveness and visibility of European higher education worldwide and to stimulate the process of convergence of degree structures across Europe. In addition, it provides an important vehicle for the promotion of intercultural dialogue between the European Union and the rest of the world.

The Erasmus+ Programme aims at promoting equity and inclusion by facilitating the access to participants with disadvantaged backgrounds and fewer opportunities compared to their peers whenever disadvantage limits or prevents participation in transnational activities for reasons such as:

- disability (i.e. participants with special needs): people with mental (intellectual, cognitive, learning), physical, sensory or other disabilities;
- educational difficulties: young people with learning difficulties; early school-leavers; low qualified adults; young people with poor school performance;
- economic obstacles: people with a low standard of living, low income, dependence on social welfare system or homeless; young people in long-term unemployment or poverty; people in debt or with financial problems;
- cultural differences: immigrants or refugees or descendants from immigrant or refugee families; people belonging to a national or ethnic minority; people with linguistic adaptation and cultural inclusion difficulties;
- health problems: people with chronic health problems, severe illnesses or psychiatric conditions;
- social obstacles: people facing discrimination because of gender, age, ethnicity, religion, sexual orientation, disability, etc.; people with limited social skills or anti-social or risky behaviours; people in a precarious situation; (ex-)offenders, (ex-)drug or alcohol abusers; young and/or single parents; orphans;
- geographical obstacles: people from remote or rural areas; people living in small islands or in peripheral regions;

5.1 Erasmus+ Program Initiatives and Activities

5.1.1 Individual learning Mobility

Action 1 provides Support for high-quality joint masters courses (Action 1 A) and doctoral programs (Action 1 B) offered by a consortium of European and possibly third-country higher education institutions. Other types of organizations concerned with the content and

outcomes of the joint program can participate in the consortium. Scholarships/fellowships for the third-country and European students/doctoral candidates respectively to follow these Erasmus Mundus joint master's courses and doctoral programs. Short-term scholarships for third-country and European academics to carry out research or teaching assignments as part of the joint master's programs. This Action fosters cooperation between higher education institutions and academic staff in Europe and third countries with a view to creating poles of excellence and providing highly trained human resources.

Erasmus+ Program Initiatives	Projects and activities
1) Individual Mobility	<p>Key Action 1 Individual learning mobility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree (EMJMD) -Higher Education students and staff -VET learners and staff -Adult Education staff - Young people and youth workers <p>Key Action 2 Cooperation for innovation and exchange of good practices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Partnership in the field of education ,training and youth -Capacity building in the field of H.E and youth. -Alliances : Knowledge and skills <p>Key Action 3 Policy innovation initiatives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Support European policy tools -Youth dialogue projects -Support for policy reforms -Stakeholder dialogue, policy program promotion. -Transparency and recognition of skills - Cooperation with international organizations with high Analytical capacity e.g OECD.
2) Jean Monnet Activities	<p>European Education (Chairs, Modules and center of excellence)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Policy debate with academic world -Support to association -Provide operating grants to designated institutions to Organize studies and conferences.
3) Sports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Small cooperative partnerships -NGO European sport events

Figure 5:Erasmus+ Program Initiatives and activities

Joint programs must involve mobility between the institutions of the consortium and lead to the award of recognized joint, double or multiple degrees to successful students / doctoral candidates. The indicative budget breakdown and number of outputs foreseen for the different activities covered by Action 1 in the period 2009-2013 is on (Figure 6.0).

Action 2: Erasmus+ Partnerships aims at promoting institutional cooperation and mobility activities between Europe and third-country Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This

Action anchors on the previous EU program External Cooperation Window (2006-2008) with wider geographical coverage, a larger scope, and differentiated objectives.

Action 2 covers two strands:

- EMA2 - STRAND1: Partnerships with countries covered by the ENPI, DCI, EDF, IPA, and ICI (ICI +) instruments⁶ (former External Cooperation Window);
- EMA2 - STRAND2: Partnerships with countries and territories covered by the Industrialized Countries Instrument (ICI) ⁷.

Action 2 provides; Support for the establishment of cooperation partnerships between European HEIs and HEIs from targeted third countries/territories with the objective of organizing and implementing structured individual mobility arrangements between the European and the third-country/territories partners. Scholarships of various lengths - depending on the priorities defined for the third countries/territories concerned, the level of studies or the particular arrangements agreed within the partnership – for and third-country/territory individuals (students, scholars, researchers, professionals).

In the call to promote Erasmus+ mobility and partnerships with the third world H.E institutions, Marilena and Konstantinos (Co-founders of WeAfriHug and YouthHub Initiatives) have been visiting African countries to seal MOU's deals in the Erasmus+ mobility scheme.

The MOU's include: In Kenya – Kenyatta University and Machakos University (MOU with the University of West Attica and University of Piraeus), in Uganda- Kyambogo University, Kampala International University, Besitema University (MOU with University of West Attica), in Tanzania – University of Dar es Salam ,in Ghana – University of Ghana, Tamale Technical University and University of Cape Coast and, in Nigeria – University of Jos.

Action 3: Promotion Projects, provide support to transnational initiatives, studies, projects, events and other activities aimed at enhancing the attractiveness, profile, image and visibility of, and accessibility to, European higher education in the world. Action 3 activities related to the international dimension of all aspects of higher education, such as promotion, accessibility, quality assurance, credit recognition, recognition of European qualifications abroad and mutual recognition of qualifications with third countries, curriculum development, mobility, quality of services, etc.

Activities may include the promotion of the Erasmus Mundus Programme and its outputs implemented by mixed networks of European and third-country organizations active in the

field of higher education. Action 3 activities may take various forms (conferences, seminars, workshops, studies, analyses, pilot projects, prizes, international networks, production of material for publication, development of information, communication and technology tools) and may take place anywhere in the world.

Action 3 activities seek to establish links between higher education and research and higher education and the private sector in European and third countries and exploit potential synergies whenever possible. The Action 3 budget for the entire duration of the Programme amounts to € 16 million and should lead to the funding of around 50 projects.

	Expected number of outputs by 2013	Estimated total budget (in million €)
Joint Programmes		
Erasmus Mundus Masters Courses (EMMCs)	150	19
Erasmus Mundus Doctorate Programmes (EMJDs)	35	6
<i>Total Joint Programme</i>	185	25
Individual scholarships / fellowships		
Category A scholarships for Masters students ³	5.300	245
Category B scholarships for Masters students	3.400	63
Category A fellowships for doctoral candidates	440	35
Category B fellowships for doctoral candidates	330	30
Scholarships for third-country scholars in EMMCs	1.900	28
Scholarships for European scholars in EMMCs	1.900	28
<i>Total scholarships / fellowships</i>	13.270	429
<i>Total indicative budget</i>		454

Figure 6: The indicative budget breakdown and number of foreseen activities (2009-2013)

5.1.2 Jean Monnet Initiative

Jean Monnet Projects support innovation, cross-fertilization and the spread of European Union content; "Innovation" projects explore new angles and different methodologies to make EU subjects more attractive and adapted to various populations, "Cross-fertilization" projects promote discussion and reflection on EU issues and enhance knowledge about the Union and its processes, "Spread content" projects concern information and dissemination activities

(Smith, 2013) argues that exchange programs are on an accelerated basis and the pool of participating students should expand to incorporate developing countries; exchange students, teachers, and school administrators will gain knowledge and experience that not only will decrease ethnocentrism, but also may contribute to rising academic standards and accomplishments in both the developed and the developing world. Moreover, studying abroad also benefits to enhance international skills, facilitating former students to be competitive in the international job market and also contributes to the motivation of such students to work abroad later in life (González, 2011). In the end, Erasmus+ Programs and initiatives tend to boost the universities in their endeavors to implement all the SDGs through research, youth empowerment, teaching, governance, and partnerships all around the world. The relationship created is a combination of various stakeholders within the society who work together to attain a common goal as shown in figure 7.0.

Figure 7: Relationship between Erasmus+ Program and Universities to implement SDGs

6. Conclusion

The United Nations' Transforming Our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development is one of the most ambitious and important global agreements in recent history. To create a more sustainable world and to engage with sustainability-related issues as described in the SDGs, individuals must become sustainability change-makers. They require the knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes that empower them to contribute to sustainable development. Education, therefore, is crucial for the achievement of sustainable development.

However, not all kinds of education support sustainable development. Education that promotes economic growth only may lead to an increase in unsustainable consumption patterns. The well-established approach of ESD empowers learners to make informed decisions and responsible actions for environmental integrity, economic viability and just society for present and future generations. All educational institutions must consider it their responsibility to deal intensively with sustainable development issues, to foster the development of sustainability competencies and to develop the specific learning outcomes related to all SDGs. Therefore, it is vital not only to include SDG-related content in the curricula but also to use action-oriented transformative pedagogy.

The above short review provides general tools and guidance for achieving SDGs for the universities that can be customized to different contexts and needs. There is no 'right' way for a university to engage with the SDGs. How universities choose to act will depend on their size, context, research or educational strengths, funding availability, values, priorities and the needs of the communities that they serve. This review outlines general concepts, steps to help tailor an approach.

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